

Research Survey

Dear students, please answer the questions below and thank you for contributing to this study! Your anonymous responses will be used solely for the teaching assistant's research on possible challenges applying SusAF and perceived possible cognitive biases in the (hidden for the review) course. By continuing with this survey, you acknowledge that your participation is voluntary, your responses are anonymous, and your data will be used exclusively for doctoral research.

1. Are you currently working in software development, or do you have any prior experience in the field? For how many years?
2. Did you notice any cognitive biases during SuSAF? Can you describe it?
3. Was it difficult to consider the sustainability impacts of your proposed solution?
4. What aspects made the impact analysis challenging?
 - a. Could you elaborate on your previous answer, or add any additional insights?
5. Did you notice any cognitive biases during teamwork (between your group members)?
6. What were the main struggles your group faced? (it can be related to cognitive biases or in general)
7. Were there any cognitive biases that you feel might have arisen during your course work (even if you're not fully sure)? For example, during innovation, market analysis, development phase? If yes, where?